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Flensburg University of Applied Sciences

Master Thesis

Topic:	Lidar Assisted Control Enhancements of Wind Turbines' Synthetic Inertia
by:	Abdelrahman Mosa
Student ID number:	650813
Degree course:	Wind Engineering Master
Supervisor and primary evaluator:	David Schlipf
Secondary evaluator:	Feng Guo
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I hereby confirm that this thesis is my own work and was completed without any unauthorised assistance. I have not used any sources apart from those indicated in the list of references.

Abstract

When the electrical grid transitions from synchronous machine generation to an inverter connected renewable resources generation, the grid's stability decreases which, correlates to the lower inertia response of the grid's generation sources. This study proposes a synthetic inertia response controller for a wind turbine, which regulates the response aggressiveness based on lidar measured wind speed. When testing this controller, modeling of a frequency signal was also required.

Testing that this method would be a better way to control wind turbines' synthetic inertia response, models of the turbine and the controller simulate multiple situations to test the controller's performance. In addition to analyzing measured samples of frequency time series and generating an expression to simulate frequency disturbance through Fourier transform. A frequency signal is produced and used to simulate the turbine with different rates of change of frequency levels. The proposed synthetic inertia controller has promising results.

The controller has a better synthetic inertia response during emergency cases while having no sign of dramatically increasing loads, as shown by the simulations.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Background

The grid is normally operated by fossil fuel engines coupled to synchronous generators, which defined some of the grid's features like the inherent inertia, and the correlation between real power and frequency, as well as reactive power and voltage. Since that there is always an imbalance between power production and consumption, the frequency of the grid is always changing slightly and not constant. This difference in power can be related to the rate of change of frequency (ROCOF). However such properties do not exist within the inverter connected renewable power plants, calling for an example wind turbines normally interface with the grid through a converter. Such a connection allows the wind turbine to output its energy to the grid with the grid's properties like frequency and voltage, while the wind turbine machinery might be operating at different and changing frequencies and voltages. The lack of a direct interface between the turbine machinery and the grid while enabling the flow of power from the wind turbine transforms the wind turbine into a passive source of energy because it will not react to the changes of the grid as a synchronous machine would. One of those changes is the inherent inertia response of a synchronous machine, where the increasing power demand would slow down the turbine and release more power from the stored kinetic energy of the machine, and vice-versa. However, the converter can be controlled to mimic the inherent behavior of the synchronous machine in the case of an existing ROCOF, which is called synthetic inertia response. The synthetic inertia control is usually added to wind turbines to improve

their service to the grid [8].

With the increasing integration of wind turbines in the grid in Germany, some modifications to the wind turbine control must be made to ensure grid stability in the future. The fast frequency response method might be used to ensure that wind turbines respond quickly to frequency disturbance, giving the grid electrical energy proportional to the frequency deviation, to counteract the effects of reduced inertia. Decreasing the number of synchronous generators in the grid means smaller inertia constant in the power system. Wind turbines as renewable energy resources have an advantage, which is having rotating masses, where kinetic inertia could be stored. Inertia response could be simulated by controlling the extraction of the kinetic energy from the rotor [3]. In the case of high ROCOF, the wind turbine should compensate using synthetic inertia.

The baseline wind turbine control algorithm consists of 5 regions, the operation of the turbine in any of the regions is defined by the wind speed; In region 1 the algorithm is to do nothing because the wind speed is less than the cut-in wind speed. the cut-in wind speed is the slowest speed at which the turbine can generate power. In region 1.5 the turbine is increasing its rotor rotational speed from zero to the optimal rotor rotational speed at the cut-in wind speed. In region 2 is the rotor rotational speed is defined by keeping the tip speed ratio (TSR) to an optimal value described by the relation in Eq. 2.1, to ensure that the wind turbine has the highest aerodynamic efficiency. In region 2.5 the turbine is increasing the rotor rotational speed to a target rotor rotational speed defined by the algorithms of region 3. In region 3 the turbine can be operated in two manners either to keep the output power constant or to keep the torque of the turbine constant, defining the target rotor rotational speed, however, this study will focus on the operation in region 2.

Many synthetic inertia response controllers were developed applying many topologies, Although they all stem from the same general idea, they are widely variant in application methods and details considered or simulated by each controller [10]. This study will consider a synthetic inertia controller, the response of which will be proportional to the ROCOF [3]. However, the controller will be modeled after a controller that uses changing synthetic inertia constant, which changes with respect to the rotational speed of the turbine thus taking into consideration the kinetic energy present in the turbine at the time of the required inertia response [4]. This study will aim to respond to the ROCOF based on the predicted Kinetic energy of the tur-

bine, which can be achieved through measuring the upcoming wind speed and adjusting the synthetic inertia response accordingly.

Lidar technology has many benefits to wind turbines in exchange for its cost, mainly measuring the upcoming wind speed with a certain accuracy, and lidar assisted control has been proved to reduce loads. Within this study, the capability of providing a better synthetic inertia response will be examined. Measuring the upcoming wind speed would allow adjusting the inertia response according to the predicted kinetic energy. Once we know the future kinetic energy we could respond more aggressively in the case of an upcoming positive gust, increasing the output power, or less aggressively in the case of a negative gust, decreasing the output power.

Using a wind speed time-series in wind turbine simulation is now common however, using a tool to analyze the turbine's reaction to the grid's changing frequency is not, that's why it is important to have a method for simulating the grid's frequency that is reproducible without the need for measured data. In turbulent wind field simulation, the Veers method is commonly used, motivated by this method the grid frequency is simulated. Analyzing the grid frequency by Fourier transform allows representing grid frequency fluctuations in the frequency domain, then the Inverse Fast Fourier Transform (IFFT) could be used to simulate a frequency time-series in the time domain [11].

1.2 Related Work

In [5], a detailed report compared the variable and the constant synthetic inertia response from many points of view, one of which was the cost of energy, concluding that using one of both controllers does not affect the cost of energy, and that the variable inertia response control resulted in fewer loads than the constant synthetic inertia response, it is also important to remark that all but 3 sensors had an increase in loads less than 1% and the other sensors did not exceed a 2.15% increase in loads in normal conditions using a middle value of inertia constants for synchronous generators according to their references.

In [6], the paper set out to find the distribution of different ROCOF levels across the operation time, while answering that question it was pointed out that as the share of inverter connected renewable energy sources increase their share in the grid, the standard deviation of the ROCOF will increase,

due to the lack of inertia provision from conventional energy sources, and derived an expression to express said change in different load levels. Based on this information, while simulating the normal turbulence operation of the turbine, the simulation was carried out with different frequency disturbance time-series having different values of the standard deviation of the ROCOF.

In [9] a robust method was developed to measure the incoming wind speed. This study will focus on determining whether or not a model of lidar assisted control will be able to better the synthetic inertia response of a wind turbine, by comparing the performance of the proposed controllers with the variable synthetic inertia provision controller.

1.3 Motivation

The purpose of this study is to examine the role of lidar in improving the synthetic inertia response. The outcome of this thesis is focusing on the potential of the lidar technology in improving the grid services of the wind turbine.

1.4 Research Questions

In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the following research questions have been selected to guide the study:

1. How can we get a generic signal of the grid frequency?
2. How and to what extent can the lidar technology improve the synthetic inertia response of a turbine?

1.5 Limitations

With humbling words, the author must confess that the scope of discussion in this paper might be slightly compromised because he lacks the knowledge and the experience of conducting such large academic papers individually compared to an experienced scholar.

The knowledge is also limited to previous education and the references quoted in this paper, other references could also be viable but were not considered during the writing of this paper.

Time is always a restricting factor in such studies, due to the lack of it, when the writer started this thesis he had small knowledge about the topic and with the time that knowledge grew, however, the time given was enough to adequately cover the topic.

Using a single degree of freedom model limits the changes that could be studied between the proposed controller and the already established controller, also disabling some features such as the damping of the controller at a high tower top displacement or limiting the pitching of the blades.

The method for simulating the frequency is also limited to uniformity, meaning that using IFFT to simulate the signal's statistics will result in a uniform output, which is hard to simulate an emergency event such as the disconnection of a power generating unit.

The method used to predict the rotor rotational speed using the lidar measurements utilizes the same system dynamics due to the simplicity of the simulation model. As the system would be more complicated the simulation would need to be more complex to predict with the same accuracy, which might cost more processing time.

The lidar measured wind speeds in this study are assumed to be a perfect measurement, however, that is not true due to the breaking of small eddies. those vanishing eddies reduce the correlation between the measured wind speeds and the actual wind speeds but only in certain for certain high frequencies.

1.6 Study Outline

This study consists of 6 chapters, which are organized in the following manner:

Chapter 1 gives an introduction to the study by describing the background, motivation and limitations of the study while stating as well the research questions.

Chapter 2 discusses the methodology followed to proceed through the study by examining some of the related work and the construction of the controller model.

Chapter 3 explains the steps followed to generate a frequency time-series from a Power density spectrum curve of a measured frequency time-series, while also viewing the results of that method.

Chapter 4 goes into details about the constructed model and the flow of the simulation.

Chapter 5 examines the results of the simulation.

Chapter 6 concludes the study based on the findings of the simulation results.

Chapter 2

Methodology

2.1 Literature Review

The synthetic inertia response algorithm used in this study depends on predicting the rotor rotational speed based on the lidar measurements. Since the study will focus on the operation in region 2 of wind turbine control. The goal of this region is to achieve maximum efficiency, by maintaining the optimum value of the TSR. Making the rotor rotational speed directly proportional to the wind speed in this control region, while having in mind that the wind speed changes stochastically. It should be noted that the inertia response is calculated based on the instantaneous rotational speed of the rotor. Undoubtedly the rotor speed changes with the wind speed, resulting in an inherently stochastic inertia response-ability.

$$\lambda = \frac{\Omega * R}{v_0} \quad (2.1)$$

where :

- λ is the TSR,
- Ω is the rotor rotational speed,
- R is the distance between the center of the hub and the tip of the turbine's blade and
- v_0 is the wind speed.

and from Eq. 2.1, Eq. 2.2 can be concluded.

$$v_0 \propto \Omega \quad (2.2)$$

The synthetic inertia definition in [3] mentioned having the constant of synthetic inertia (H_{syn}) " defined by the relationship between the terminal frequency and change in electrical power of the generator".

Also considered as an approximation of the swing equation, which concluded a general expression as seen in Eq. 2.3 many topologies can be used to achieve synthetic (virtual) inertia response the one used in this study is closer to the swing equation model presented in [10] however it must be noted that no damping was considered.

$$\frac{2H}{f_{grid}} \frac{df}{dt} = \frac{P_{Gen} - P_{Load}}{S_g} \quad (2.3)$$

where:

- P_{gen} is the total generated electrical power in the system [W],
- P_{load} is the total consumed electrical power in the system [W],
- S_g is the rated output apparent power of the system [VA],
- H is the inertia constant of the power system [s],
- $\frac{df}{dt}$ is the ROCOF [Hz/s],
- and f is the frequency [Hz].

According to [4] the expression of synthetic inertia response can also be written as seen in Eq. 2.4.

$$P_{SI, \text{fixed-H}} = -2H_{\text{dem}}P_{\text{rated}}\frac{ROCOF}{f_{\text{grid}}} \quad (2.4)$$

where:

- $P_{SI, \text{fixed-H}}$ is the inertia response electrical output power of the turbine,
- P_{rated} is the rated electrical output power of the turbine,
- H_{dem} is the constant of synthetic inertia demanded by the grid operator,
- $ROCOF$ is the ROCOF,
- and f_{grid} is the frequency.

In [4] it was proved that using variable synthetic inertia constant (H_{var}) ensures that the wind turbine has continuous synthetic inertia provision at all operating points, making wind turbines a more dependable synthetic inertia source in the grid, as well as avoiding unnecessary disconnection from the grid, because it would avoid the extraction of more than the available kinetic energy from the turbine reducing the rotor rotational speed below cut in, these benefits are maintained by scaling the synthetic inertia factor in relation to the available kinetic energy as it would be calculated in Eq. 2.5.

$$\frac{H_{\text{var}}}{H_{\text{dem}}} = \frac{0.5J_{\text{WTG}}(\omega_{\text{gen}}^2 - \omega_{\text{cut-in}}^2)}{0.5J_{\text{WTG}}(\omega_{\text{rated}}^2 - \omega_{\text{cut-in}}^2)} \quad (2.5)$$

where :

- H_{var} is the variable constant of synthetic inertia,
- H_{dem} is the constant of synthetic inertia demanded by the grid operators,
- J_{WTG} is the mass moment of inertia of the wind turbine,
- and ω is the rotor rotational speed where the subscripts gen, rated and cut-in specify current, rated and cut in rotational speeds respectively.

From Eq. 2.4 and Eq. 2.5, the expression of the synthetic inertia response power (P_{SI}) changed into a form which can be seen in Eq. 2.6.

$$P_{SI, \text{var-H}} = -2H_{\text{var}}P_{\text{rated}}\frac{ROCOF}{f_{\text{grid}}} \quad (2.6)$$

in this paper lidar calculated kinetic energy will replace the instantaneous kinetic energy of the turbine, either by calculating the kinetic energy in a single moment in the predicted future or as an average of the kinetic energy over an upcoming predicted period. Information about the upcoming wind speed is the contributing factor here in the calculation of the future kinetic energy of the turbine and consequently the synthetic inertia response.

2.2 Controller Model Construction

In order to observe the difference between the lidar assisted synthetic inertia and the variable synthetic inertia at a basic level, the simulation model of the wind turbine is constructed on MATLAB Simulink to be a single degree of freedom model. the frequency of the grid and the rotor effective wind speeds are the disturbances considered, the two wind speeds applied to the model are the wind speed affecting the drive-train directly at the time of the simulation and the wind speed measured by the lidar. The controller model is based on the feedback controller of the turbine, apart from the added block of the synthetic inertia and the torque control block which can be seen in Fig. 2.1.

Figure 2.1: Overview of the Simulink Model

Figure 2.2: simplified view of the Simulink model

In the synthetic inertia block with the knowledge about the upcoming wind, the turbine control parameters and the system dynamics, the rotor rotational speed can be calculated, from which the expected available kinetic energy is calculated over a period of time that is allowed by the lidar, in this example, the time was taken to be 5 seconds, as the input is a perfect 5 seconds future preview of the wind from the lidar, and then averaged over a 4.625 seconds period to get a representation of the available kinetic energy in that period.

Extracting kinetic energy from the wind turbine is done by the converter, where the converter would allow more electrical current to flow causing an increase in output power as well as an increase of the load torque on the wind turbine, in this manner the output of the synthetic inertia controller is the torque which added to the torque of the generator allows for an increase or a decrease in output power. All the variable parameters needed for calculating the output torque are measured or calculated, such as the frequency, ROCOF, the variable synthetic inertia constant and the rotor rotational speed all of which are used in Eq. 2.6 except for the rotor rotational speed which is used in calculating the torque from the power expression.

However, calculating the variable synthetic inertia constant requires the current rotational speed according to [6] and the lidar predicted rotor rotational speed or averaged rotor rotational speed in this study to be able to answer the research questions.

Predicting the rotor rotational speed is based on the lidar measured wind speed and feedback of the turbine controller and system dynamics, having the system simulated in such a manner can accurately predict the rotor rotational speed. However, it must be noted that the dynamics of the model are not true in real life, because the system dynamics of an actual turbine are much more complicated in real life. As well as the assumption of having a perfect view of the wind, which ignores the decreased correlation of the measured wind speeds at higher frequencies of the wind Fourier transform. A diagram explaining the flow of the synthetic inertia controller constructed in this paper is shown in Fig. 2.3, showing the most important details about the flow of the controller.

Figure 2.3: Simplified view of the synthetic inertia control

where:

- block (1) is the block in which the predicted rotor rotational speed is calculated using the lidar measured wind speed and the system feedback including the generator torque and the pitch angle,
- block (2) is the block in which the synthetic inertia constant is scaled from the value demanded by the grid operator to the new value, based on either the current rotor rotational speed, predicted rotor rotational speed or the average predicted rotor rotational speed,
- block (3) is the block in which the synthetic inertia response is calculated using the variable synthetic inertia constant, the rated power, the grid frequency, the ROCOF, and the current generator rotational speed, the value of the response was often referred to as power in the literature, however, the controller changes the value of the power through the manipulating the value of the generator torque. That being said the output power required by the grid is then calculated as an excess generator torque, by dividing the required power over the current generator rotational speed.

Chapter 3

Frequency Time-Series Generation

As previously mentioned the frequency time-series can be generated through the inverse Fourier transform of a similar power spectrum density (PSD) curve. Before deciding on extrapolating a PSD curve fit, some frequency analysis was first needed in order to do understand the given data to an extent, due to time limitations it was only possible to analyze one month of the available data.

Figure 3.1: Wind energy production share for the year 2018 [2]

It can be noted that in Fig. 3.1 that the wind energy yield of each month is not the same. this difference in yield is there due to an existing annual wind pattern, where the monthly average wind speed changes throughout

the year, resulting in a change in energy yield. The measurements of the month of October 2018 was chosen as it has a medium share of wind energy production compared to the rest of the year, and the following analysis will be conducted on it.

3.1 Analysis

To generate a reference PSD curve, many samples of measurements must be analyzed to ensure that the PSD curves of the different samples of frequencies have a general trend. Luckily Flensburg university of applied sciences' Wind Energy Technology Institute (WETI) measures the frequency with a 0.1638 seconds time step. Having access to this data, it was split into hours, and each hour was analyzed by Welch's method (a method used to do the inverse Fourier transform), through plotting all of them together the results could be seen in Fig.3.2 where the blue line is the mean value of the spectra of all hours, and the black lines show the standard deviation of the spectra at that frequency :

Figure 3.2: PSD estimates of every hour in one month

Although the PSD curves have slight differences in shape and power, they all seem to be following a similar trend. That trend is close to a straight line

in the logarithmic scale. Replicating the PSD curve, a straight line will be fitted to the spectra and will be used to generate a similar time series by applying an inverse Fourier transform to the PSD curve.

Other trends could be seen as well such as the average frequency, the standard deviation of the frequency, and the standard deviation of the ROCOF. these trends can be useful when doing a more accurate simulation when a certain day or a certain hour needs to be simulated.

In Fig. 3.3, the average of the frequency has a trend where it would decline through the day, although there are minor jumps, up to a specific hour at which the frequency jumps back up considerably then begin to decrease again throughout the next day. While simulating that trend can be modeled as a reverse saw wave having a different average frequency each day.

Figure 3.3: the average frequency of samples

The value of the average of the standard deviations of the frequency is low for most of the working hours. And throughout the working hours, the standard deviation of the frequency sticks to a tight band. While in some other hours, it is hard to define a specific value for the standard deviation, as data samples exist in a bigger band. Considering the simulation hour while simulating is needed. Since the target standard deviation of a specific hour will be different based on the characteristics in Fig.3.4.

Figure 3.4: the standard deviation of the frequency samples

In Fig. 3.5, it is clear that the standard deviation of the ROCOF isn't higher than 5.5×10^{-3} or lower than 3×10^{-3} . When generating a frequency time-series, those bounds are helpful to scale the Fourier series of the frequency to have the desired ROCOF level be within realistic limits.

Figure 3.5: the standard deviation of the ROCOF of samples

3.2 Fitting

To be able to make a precise fit, the trend of the PSD curves only is needed. That's why all the calculated PSD curves were divided by the variance of their respective frequency samples, causing the resultant PSD curves to have the same variance value of unity. The required value of the standard deviation of the ROCOF can be adjusted by a factor later.

It is significant to have a limited number of smooth PSD curves from the measured data. Consequently, the PSD curves of a specific hour are averaged throughout the month, resulting in 24 averaged PSD curves instead of 744 unique PSD curves, having multiple different noisy trends.

Optimization problems have three parts. The first part is the constraint equation. Since the wind reconstruction method is the basis for this method, the equation used to produce the frequency PSD curve is derived from the equation that generates the wind PSD curve, being Eq. 3.1 in this problem. The second part is the optimization equation. This optimization equation aims to decrease the differences between the logarithmic values of two points on the fitted and the original curve. Being Eq. 3.2 in this problem. The third and final part is the optimization parameters, being the function $g(b, c)$ and the variables b and c .

$$PSD = \frac{g(b, c)}{(1 + b * f)^c} \quad (3.1)$$

$$error = \sum_{i=f_{min}}^{f_{max}} |\log S_{fit,i} - \log S_{welch,i}| \quad (3.2)$$

The function $g(b, c)$ was calculated through analysis of Eq. 3.1. The PSD curves are divided by the variance value of their respective frequency signals. Consequently, the integration of PSD curves with respect to the frequency is unity. Through the integration of Eq. 3.1. we can conclude Eq. 3.7.

$$\int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} PSD = \int_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \frac{g(b, c)}{(1 + b * f)^c} df \quad (3.3)$$

$$1 = \left[\frac{g(b, c)}{(1 - c) * b} * (1 + bf)^{1-c} \right]_{f_{min}}^{f_{max}} \quad (3.4)$$

$$1 = \left[\frac{g(b, c)}{(1 - c) * b} * [(1 + b * f_{max})^{1-c} - (1 + b * f_{min})^{1-c}] \right] \quad (3.5)$$

$$1 = \left[g(b, c) * \frac{[(1 + b * f_{max})^{1-c} - (1 + b * f_{min})^{1-c}]}{(1 - c) * b} \right] \quad (3.6)$$

$$g(b, c) = \frac{(1 - c) * b}{[(1 + b * f_{max})^{1-c} - (1 + b * f_{min})^{1-c}]} \quad (3.7)$$

By excluding the function $g(b, c)$ as an optimization factor, only two optimization parameters remain in the constraint equation, written as Eq. 3.8.

$$PSD = \frac{(1 - c) * b}{[(1 + b * f_{max})^{1-c} - (1 + b * f_{min})^{1-c}] * (1 + b * f)^c} \quad (3.8)$$

3.3 Output

One of the results is Fig. 3.6. As there are many results, the one selected for this study has the least error. All errors and other fittings are shown in the appendix Tab. 6.11 and Figs. 6.1(a) to 6.1(x). Fig. 3.7 shows a comparison between a sample of the measured frequency time-series and a generated frequency time-series and, and Fig. 3.8 their ROCOF. The measured data is a sample from the same month of the parent analysis data and the same hour of the average fitted PSD curves. The factor calculated to scale the produced data makes the standard deviation of both ROCOFs time-series the same, as the ROCOF is the main variable in calculating the frequency response. Both frequency time-series have the same average frequency value.

Figure 3.6: fitted PSD with relation to

Figure 3.7: Simulated Frequency and a Measured sample frequency

Figure 3.8: Simulated ROCOF and the Measured sample's ROCOF

Chapter 4

Model

4.1 Wind Turbine Modelling for Controller Design

A single degree of freedom model (rotor axis) was used to mainly study the power provision differences between the lidar assisted synthetic inertia control and the normal variable synthetic inertia control in addition to the simplicity of a controller made for a single degree of freedom system. the system can be described through three equations, being the output electrical power of the turbine, the rotor rotational acceleration, and the aerodynamic torque, described in Eqs. 4.1,4.2 and 4.3

$$P_{el} = M_G \frac{\Omega}{i_{GB}} \eta_{el} \quad (4.1)$$

The electrical output power P_{el} is calculated by multiplying the generator torque M_G with the angular speed of the generator shaft $\Omega_G = \frac{\Omega}{i_{GB}}$ and the efficiency of the Generator η .

$$J\dot{\Omega} = M_a - \frac{M_G}{i_{GB}} \quad (4.2)$$

The angular acceleration $\dot{\Omega}$ can be calculated through the difference between the aerodynamic torque M_a and the generator torque M_G , referred to the rotor side and then divided by the mass moment of inertia J .

$$M_a = \frac{P_a}{\Omega} = \frac{0.5\rho\pi R^2 C_p(\theta, \lambda)v_0^3}{\Omega} \quad (4.3)$$

The aerodynamic torque however, is calculated by dividing the aerodynamic power by the rotor rotational speed Ω , the aerodynamic power is calculated from the famous 1 2 3 equation where ρ is the air density, R is the rotor diameter, v_0 is the wind speed ahead of the turbine, C_P is the coefficient of power which is a function in both the pitch of the blades θ and the tip speed ratio λ .

4.2 Lidar Based Rotational Speed Estimator

Knowing the future wind speed, the future rotor speed can be calculated through simulated system dynamics and control strategy, for a single degree of freedom model and a straight forward control strategy, this simulation will not consume much time, nonetheless, it should be considered that a more accurate simulation of the system dynamics, or a more complicated control strategy will consume more time, resulting in a smaller period over which the future wind speed is averaged. For this model Eqs. 4.4. and 4.5 are used to describe the system dynamics are defined as follows:

$$J\dot{\Omega}_{lidar} = \frac{0.5\rho\pi R^2 C_p(\theta, \lambda)v_{0L}^3}{\Omega} - \frac{M_G}{i_{GB}} \quad (4.4)$$

$$J\dot{\Omega}_{SI} = - \frac{M_{SI}}{i_{GB}} \quad (4.5)$$

through the defined equations we can calculate the Omega of the rotor with only one factor that could create a difference, being the ROCOF, while the wind speed might be known for a certain upcoming period the frequency remains unpredictable, which is why we need to consider it as well the effect of the synthetic inertia torque on the rotor speed in order to further correct the Ω_{lidar} prediction, shown in equation (3.5) is the difference that it would have and that difference on the Ω should be added as well to the other for the next loop only, as it will be considered in M_G in the next loop.

The turbine chosen for this study is the IEA 3.4 MW land based turbine[1], and the values that are used in simulating the turbine dynamics can be found Appendix Tabs. 6.4 and 6.5.

4.3 Disturbances Modelling

There are mainly two scenarios that happen in a grid. One is an emergency where usually a generator disconnects or a huge load is suddenly demanded, leading to a great difference between the generation and consumption of power, reducing the Frequency and resulting in a huge ROCOF, and the other way around as well. For synchronous generators, the input power can be changed, however, wind turbines while being able to modulate power can only extract kinetic energy from the rotor to increase the output power. the first scenario while occurring several times in the grid, is not the normal operation condition, the normally occurring operation condition is the normal turbulence mode.

The wind speed can also change significantly in a short period, which can correspond to the first frequency change scenario and that possibility should be considered, while also considering the normal turbulence mode to see the effects on the turbine operation.

Enabling the simulation to be reproducible the disturbances needed to be re-creatable. That is the reason why the disturbances were created in the manner they were. To be able to answer all research questions constructing two scenarios were needed, each having their distinctive wind and frequency disturbance.

4.3.1 Emergency case

Answering the second research question required a setting in which a huge drop in frequency combined with a sudden wind gust is simulated, to view the behavior of the controller.

Extreme change in wind speed

For the wind, an extreme operating wind gust profile was generated in compliance with the latest IEC standard, with a base wind speed of 8 [m/s]. The base wind speed was chosen in a way that the turbine operation remains within the constraints of region 2 of the wind turbine control.

Frequency

as for the frequency disturbance, a swing equation model for experiencing a step loss in generation power, leading to a drop in the frequency was

simulated. The transfer function for the linear model of the power system, which contains additionally a low pass filter, is written as in Eq. 4.6.

$$TF = \frac{G s \omega^2}{(s^2 + 2D\omega s + \omega^2) * (sT + 1)} \quad (4.6)$$

where:

- TF is the transfer function presenting the power system model,
- ω is the frequency of the power system model,
- D is the damping of the power system model,
- G is the gain of the power system model,
- T is the rising time of the additional low pass filter.

4.3.2 Turbulent case

Providing an answer for the second question also required a setting testing normal turbulent variations in wind speed and frequency, to study the controller's effect on the turbine, mainly whether it would have a significant difference in the produced power and would the controller aid the turbine to better adhere to the rated power coefficient during normal operation.

Turbulent wind

A normal turbulence mode wind of class IIIA files generated by TurbSim [7] were used to generate wind time-series. Calculating the effective rotor wind speed is done by averaging the wind speeds of the nodes that are crossing the circular area, which is defined by the distance from the center of the hub to the tip of one of the blades of the turbine as its radius.

Figure 4.1: turbulent wind time series

Frequency

The frequency was generated by simulating the PSD curve in Ch. 3 using inverse fast Fourier transformation and the frequency used for this simulation is the same as the one in Fig. 3.7.

Chapter 5

Simulation Result

Based on the model and the disturbances described in the previous chapters, the simulation takes place. In this chapter, the results of the simulations of both previously mentioned scenarios are discussed.

The controller has four different configurations, all of them simulated in all the previously mentioned scenarios. The modes are as follows:

- No synthetic inertia response.
- Variable synthetic inertia response. The mode in which using the current rotor rotational speed of the generator, the synthetic inertia response is calculated (referred to as variable synthetic inertia through this paper).
- Variable synthetic inertia response. The mode in which using the predicted rotor rotational speed of the generator, the synthetic inertia response is calculated (referred to as lidar synthetic inertia).
- Variable synthetic inertia response. The mode in which using the averaged kinetic energy predicted by the lidar over an upcoming period, the synthetic inertia response is calculated (referred to as average lidar synthetic inertia).

Considering the configuration of the no synthetic inertia response as the base case to which all other modes are compared. While in some calculations, the variable synthetic inertia is the base case.

5.1 Rotational speed prediction

The quality of the controller response depends on the predicted rotor rotational speed quality. Therefore the quality of the prediction requires analysis. There are two prediction methods analyzed, the first is the measurement of just one moment, and the other is the average over several moments based on the same measured data. Figs. 5.1, 5.2, and 5.3 show the predictions of the squared generator rotational speed compared to the actual squared generator's speed, the data is squared to be a representative of the turbine's kinetic energy. Fig. 5.1 shows the prediction of the generator speed during the turbulent case simulation, which seems sufficient accurate.

Figure 5.1: The Square of the Generator Rotational Speed compared to LIDAR Prediction Normal Turbulent Case Simulation

However, during both wind gusts, the predicted generator rotational speed is slightly higher than the actual generator rotational speed. This slight difference is most likely a result of the withdrawn kinetic energy in those scenarios.

Figure 5.2: The Square of the Generator Rotational Speed compared to LIDAR Prediction Increasing Wind Gust Simulation

Figure 5.3: The Square of the Generator Rotational Speed compared to LIDAR Prediction Decreasing Wind Gust Simulation

5.2 Emergency case

In the emergency case, the possible scenario of a sudden generation power drop caused a large ROCOF. Simultaneously, the wind disturbance can also have one of two extreme possibilities, being the simulated scenarios. Which are wind gusts in both cases. One has an increasing wind gust, and the other has a decreasing wind gust. The controller tries to increase the inertia response in the event of an increase in the wind speed and vice versa. The wind turbine operation didn't exit region two during the simulations.

5.2.1 frequency drop with increasing wind gust

After simulating this case, we can observe some data from the following Figs. 5.4 and 5.5 which are:

- The shape of the effective rotor wind speed.
- The ROCOF.
- The constant pitch angle doesn't change, making sure operation remains in region 2 of turbine control.
- That there is a tiny difference in the rotor rotational speed, beginning at the same time at which the fault occurred.
- The power delivered by both lidar synthetic inertia modes is higher than that of the variable synthetic inertia mode at the peak. Both configurations remain relatively close to the variable synthetic inertia response in the settling area.

The controller here fulfilled its objectives, and it can increase power at the fault event while maintaining its recovery characteristics similar to the variable synthetic inertia controller.

Figure 5.4: Increasing wind gust simulation

Figure 5.5: Increasing wind gust simulation

5.2.2 frequency drop with decreasing wind gust

After simulating this case, we can observe some data from the following Figs. 5.6 and 5.7 which are:

- The shape of the effective rotor wind speed.
- The ROCOF.
- The constant pitch angle doesn't change, making sure operation remains in region 2 of turbine control.
- That there is a tiny difference in the rotor rotational speed between the variable synthetic inertia cases and the base case. That difference begins at the same time at which the fault occurred.
- The power delivered by both lidar synthetic inertia modes is lower than that of the variable synthetic inertia mode at the peak. Both configurations remain relatively close to the variable synthetic inertia response in the settling area.

The controller here fulfills its objectives, as it can decrease power output in this case and maintains its recovery characteristics similar to the variable synthetic inertia controller.

Figure 5.6: Decreasing wind gust simulation

Figure 5.7: Decreasing wind gust simulation

5.3 Normal turbulent case

In the normal turbulent case, the scenarios consider the usual disturbances that affect a turbine. These disturbances are the turbulent wind speed and the frequency of the grid. The standard deviation of the rotor rotational speed and the power, the root mean square of the provided inertia response, and the change in energy yield are the factors that indicate the performance of the controller. Fig. 5.8 is a sample of the simulation graphs. According to [4], the authors predict that the grid will have less inertia in the future with the increasing share of inverter-connected renewable energy sources. That's why three different ROCOF cases were simulated with each controller for the turbulent case, using the same wind speed time-series, since all controllers are extracting power proportional to the ROCOF. The standard deviations of the rotor rotational speed and power indicate if the control methods affect the loads in a more complex system. In Fig. 5.8, the following data can be noticed:

- The effective rotor wind speed.
- The pitch angle remains unchanged, ensuring that the whole simulation took place in region 2 of the wind turbine control.
- The differences between all three inertia response modes are hardly noticeable in this simulation (ROCOF level).

Figure 5.8: Normal Turbulence Simulation

In the following Figs. 5.9 and 5.10, the following can be observed:

- There is a small difference in the standard deviations of both the power and the generator rotational speed. However, concerning the standard deviation of the generator's rotational speed, the standard deviations of the lidar assisted control methods are lower, resulting in lower loads. While the average lidar synthetic inertia response has a higher standard deviation, the full numbers are in the appendix in Tab. 6.6. For the standard deviation of the power, the lidar synthetic inertia response is the highest, and the average lidar synthetic inertia is not the lowest.
- That although the values in Fig. 5.11 are almost equal at the same ROCOF. The lidar synthetic inertia control has slightly higher values than the other inertia response controls' values, while the other values are the same. On another note, the RMS of the synthetic inertia response power is proportional to the ROCOF in all the controllers. Eq. 5.1 is used to calculate the values in Fig. 5.11 :

$$P_{inertia-RMS} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{600 - 50} \int_{50}^{600} (P_{inertia-i} - P_{no-inertia})^2 dt} \quad (5.1)$$

Figure 5.9: Standard deviation of Ω_g [rpm]

Figure 5.10: Standard deviation of Power ($\times 10^5$) [W]

Where $P_{inertia-i}$ is the result power time-series of the simulation of the control method, $P_{no-inertia}$ is the result power time-series of the no inertia method, and $P_{inertia-RMS}$ is the result of the calculation. A period of 50 seconds of simulation is not considered in the beginning to reduce errors arising from oscillations taking place at that period.

Figure 5.11: RMS of the synthetic inertia power [kW]

- That synthetic inertia results in a lower energy yield in Fig. 5.12.
- That the lidar synthetic inertia control has the lowest energy yield, followed by the average lidar synthetic inertia followed by the variable synthetic inertia. The values in Fig. 5.12 are calculated using Eq. 5.2, which calculates the difference in output electrical energy in the period from 50 seconds to 600 seconds, which can be written as follows:

$$E_{difference} = \int_{50}^{600} P_{inertia-i} dt - \int_{50}^{600} P_{no-inertia} dt \quad (5.2)$$

Where $P_{inertia-i}$ and $P_{no-inertia}$ are the same as Eq. 5.1 while $E_{difference}$ is the result of the calculation. the result values are presented in Fig. 5.12.

Figure 5.12: change in energy due to inertia response [Wh]

- The average aerodynamic power coefficient is calculated for each method and compared with the value of no synthetic inertia response. Providing synthetic inertia response results in an average power coefficient decrease, while using the lidar can increase that deviation. As seen in Fig. 5.13 the lidar synthetic inertia response has the highest shift from the no inertia feedback case followed by the average lidar synthetic inertia.

Figure 5.13: percentage error of average power coefficient (c_P) ($\times 10^{-4}$) [-%]

Chapter 6

Conclusion and Future Outlook

Based on the presented results in the previous chapter, this study discusses the possibility of integrating the lidar with the synthetic inertia response and provides an output that opens the doors for future research work in lidar enhancements of grid services. This chapter will conclude the study and define some future research options.

6.1 Conclusion

Recalling on the research questions:

- Concerning the generic signal of the grid frequency, while having access to measured data is widespread. This study includes a new method inspired by the wind time-series simulation methods. The technique is: First, analyzing a large set of measured data samples, which clarifies if there is an existing trend. Ensuring that the data has a unity standard deviation value making the PSD curves easier to fit. Then, averaging many similar PSD curves to get a lower number of low noise PSD curves, each representing a period of the day. Choosing a suitable fitting formula depending on the shape of the trend and fitting each of the averaged curves. Then, applying an IFFT to the resulting PSD curve to get the signal's time-series. Assessing the generated signal quality by calculating the difference in variances of the simulated time-series with respect to their PSD curves, if there is less than 20% error between the variance of the PSD curve and the variance of the generated time-series,

then the error is acceptable. Finally, scaling the resultant time-series to the required value of the ROCOF. This technique produced the frequency time-series used for the turbulent scenarios simulation because it enabled the author to acquire different frequency time-series based on the desired ROCOF.

- Regarding the lidar technology's ability to improve the synthetic inertia response of a turbine, the synthetic inertia controller is designed to change the response intensity based on the measured upcoming wind speed. Higher upcoming wind speed correlates to higher available kinetic energy. The controller, in that case, responds more aggressively and vice versa. The controller's feedback depends on the rotor rotational speed's prediction model. Based on the results of the emergency case simulation. The wind turbine provides a better synthetic inertia response using lidar. If enough wind resource exists in the upcoming wind speed, the controller increases its output. If not, the controller produces a lower output power than the variable inertia response controller and evade the risk of disconnection.

Based on the result of the normal turbulent case. There are small differences between the results of each control method. One of them being the rotor rotational speed standard deviation values of the lidar methods are lower than the variable synthetic inertia. That can indicate lower loads in further analysis. While the lidar synthetic inertia response might have the least deviation from the optimal aerodynamic efficiency, it would have the highest loads. However, the average lidar synthetic inertia response has the highest energy change due to the synthetic inertia response.

6.2 Future Outlook

The analysis carried out in this study opens the door for more research in the future in different areas such as the analysis of the control in region 3 of wind turbine control and including a higher complexity model of the turbine dynamics, enabling the review of the load changes based on the control method.

Bibliography

- [1] Pietro Bortolotti, Helena Canet Tarrés, Katherine Dykes, Karl Merz, Latha Sethuraman, David Verelst, and Frederik Zahle. IEA Wind Task 37 on Systems Engineering in Wind Energy WP2.1 Reference Wind Turbines. Technical report, National Renewable Energy Laboratory, Golden CO, USA, Wind Energy Institute, Technische Universität München, Germany, SINTEF Energy Research AS, Trondheim, Norway, Wind Energy Department, Technical University of Denmark, Roskilde, Denmark, May 2019.
- [2] Bundesnetsagentur. wind energy consumption SMARD. Accessed : 12/9/2020.
- [3] Robert Eriksson, Niklas Modig, and Katherine Elkington. Synthetic inertia versus fast frequency response: a definition. *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 12(5):507–514, apr 2018.
- [4] Arne Gloe, Clemens Jauch, Bogdan Craciun, and Jörg Winkelmann. Continuous provision of synthetic inertia with wind turbines: implications for the wind turbine and for the grid. *IET Renewable Power Generation*, 13(5):668–675, apr 2019.
- [5] Arne Gloe, Clemens Jauch, Henning Thiesen, and Jonas Viebeg. Inertial Response Controller Design for a Variable Speed Wind Turbine. Technical report, WETI at Felsburg University of Applied Science, 03 2018.
- [6] Arne Gloe, Henning Thiesen, and Clemens Jauch. Grid Frequency Analysis for Assessing the Stress on Wind Turbines. In *Wind Integration Workshop*, Vienna, 11 2016.

- [7] B. Jonkman and Buhl Jr. TurbSim User's Guide. Technical report, National Renewable Energy Lab (NREL), 01 2007.
- [8] Erik Ørum, Mikko Kuivaniemi, Minna Laasonen, Alf Ivar Bruseth, Erik Alexander Jansson, Anders Danell, Katherine Elkington, and Niklas Modig. Future system inertia. Technical report, ENTSO-E, 2015.
- [9] David Schlipf. *Lidar-Assisted Control Concepts for Wind Turbines*. PhD thesis, Institute of Aircraft Design, University of Stuttgart, 2016.
- [10] Ujjwol Tamrakar, Dipesh Shrestha, Manisha Maharjan, Bishnu Bhattarai, Timothy Hansen, and Reinaldo Tonkoski. Virtual Inertia: Current Trends and Future Directions. *Applied Sciences*, 7(7):654, Jun 2017.
- [11] Paul Veers. Three Dimensional Wind Simulation. In *SAND88-0152*, Albuquerque, New Mexico, USA, 01 1988. Sandia National Laboratories.

Appendix

- .in file of the turbSim

Value	Variable	Description
100000	RandSeed1	- First random seed
RANLUX	RandSeed2	- Second random seed
True	Clockwise	- Clockwise rotation looking downwind?
2	ScaleIEC	- use individual scales of IEC σ
35	NumGrid Z	- Vertical grid-point matrix dimension
35	NumGrid Y	- Horizontal grid-point matrix dimension
0.125	TimeStep	- Time step [seconds]
600	AnalysisTime	- Length of analysis time series [seconds]
600	UsableTime	- Usable length of time series [seconds]
110	HubHt	- Hub height [m]
136	GridHeight	- Grid height [m]
136	GridWidth	- Grid width [m]
0	VFlowAng	- uptilt angle [degrees]
0	HFlowAng	- skew angle [degrees]
"IECKAI"	TurbModel	- Turbulence model IEC kaimal
"3"	IECstandard	- Number of IEC 61400-x standard
"A"	IECturbc	- IEC turbulence characteristic
"NTM"	IEC WindType	- Normal IEC turbulence type
110	RefHt	- Height of the reference wind speed [m]
7	URef	- Mean wind [m/s]
0.05	RICH NO	- Gradient Richardson number

Table 6.1: TurbSim wind file settings used for simulation other variables are either default or ignored

- variable values for the model in matlab

Parameter	value	description
b	1000	optimization factor b in eq.3.7
c	2.113725676965054	optimization factor c in eq.3.7
factor	$[3.5, 4.5, 5.5] * (\frac{10^{(-3)}}{0.0423})$	multiplying the coefficients of the Fourier series with this factor to control the standard deviation of the ROCOF
seed	1	the seed used to generate random phase angles for the different frequencies in MATLAB

Table 6.2: frequency variables

Parameter	value
ω	1
D	1
G	5
T	2

Table 6.3: swing model variables

turbine and turbine control parameters [1]:

Parameter	value	description
ρ	1.225	Air density [kg/m^3]
i	1/97	Gearbox ratio [-]
R	65	Rotor radius [m]
HH	108	Hub height [m]
J_G	500	Generator inertia about High-Speed shaft [kgm^2]
J_R	35799464	Rotor inertia about Low-Speed shaft [kgm^2]
J	40503964	Total turbine inertia about Low-Speed shaft [kgm^2]
η_{gb}	0.955	Gearbox efficiency [-]
η_{el}	0.98	Generator efficiency [-]

Table 6.4: matlab variables

Parameter	value	unit
gain scheduling theta	[0.058207 0.187239 0.293442 0.362697]	[rad]
gain scheduling kp	[0.042064 0.011010 0.005754 0.003851]	[s]
gain scheduling Ti	[2.864479 2.665488 2.225443 1.855480]	[s]
Ω_g rated	1139.7	[rpm]
θ_{max}	50	[deg]
θ_{min}	1.09	[deg]
k	2.1656	$[\frac{Nm}{(rad/s)^2}]$
θ_{fine}	1.5	[deg]
Mode	constant power in region 3	[-]
M_a rated	$2.925 * 10^6$	[Nm]
P_a rated	$3.4694 * 10^6$	[W]
$\Omega_{1T_{o1.5}}$	3.8	[rpm]
$\Omega_{1.5T_{o2}}$	4.8	[rpm]
$\Omega_{2T_{o2.5}}$	11.4	[rpm]
$\Omega_{2.5T_{o3}}$	11.75	[rpm]
$a_{1.5}$	506.8331040008139	$[\frac{Nm}{rad/s}]$
$b_{1.5}$	-19563.60664492334	[Nm]
$a_{2.5}$	143.9617013760758	$[\frac{Nm}{rad/s}]$
$b_{2.5}$	12369.09240950930	[Nm]

Table 6.5: matlab control variables

- table of all outputs in the simulations

σ ROCOF	No SI	Var H	Lidar H	Av. Lidar H
$3.5 * 10^{-3}$	1.56788272482828	1.56792616029558	1.56792071023503	1.56792243139465
$4.5 * 10^{-3}$	1.56788272482828	1.56793860529722	1.56793160098848	1.56793380925927
$5.5 * 10^{-3}$	1.56788272482828	1.56795106528646	1.56794250688360	1.56794520049990

Table 6.6: Standard deviation of Ω_g [rpm] (full digits)

σ ROCOF	No SI	Var H	Lidar H	Av. Lidar H
$3.5 * 10^{-3}$	800363.656616006	800332.598135297	800332.988987176	800332.820350471
$4.5 * 10^{-3}$	800363.656616006	800324.853109754	800325.357892575	800325.141227426
$5.5 * 10^{-3}$	800363.656616006	800317.609676436	800318.228503177	800317.964110168

Table 6.7: Standard deviation of Power [W] (full digits)

σ ROCOF	No SI	Var H	Lidar H	Av. Lidar H
$3.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	2437.86789709861	2439.18512393186	2437.88094447744
$4.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	3134.91727972420	3136.60899205097	3134.93053415475
$5.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	3832.19643410069	3834.26210583564	3832.20850293712

Table 6.8: RMS of synthetic inertia Power [W] (full digits)

σ ROCOF	No SI	Var H	Lidar H	Av. Lidar H
$3.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-0.00219007729265286	-0.00319987315560866	-0.00255429214280412
$4.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-0.00282503795529010	-0.00412412558716824	-0.00328778548055197
$5.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-0.00346616467618333	-0.00505683611231689	-0.00402591756028414

Table 6.9: change in energy due to inertia response [Wh] (full digits)

σ ROCOF	No SI	Var H	Lidar H	Av. Lidar H
$3.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-4.05158405749988	-4.21646242708185	-4.14383519578462
$4.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-5.21115389817312	-5.42344804567435	-5.33029208357690
$5.5 * 10^{-3}$	0	-6.37256102817177	-6.63217955251644	-6.51853355816212

Table 6.10: percentage error of average power coefficient (c_P) ($*10^{-4}$) [-] (full digits)

- Pictures of all the outputs of the frequency fitting and the errors, std. Fitting of all hours :

(a) fitting of hour 1

(b) fitting of hour 2

(c) fitting of hour 3

(d) fitting of hour 4

(e) fitting of hour 5

(f) fitting of hour 6

(g) fitting of hour 7

(h) fitting of hour 8

(i) fitting of hour 9

(j) fitting of hour 10

(k) fitting of hour 11

(l) fitting of hour 12

(m) fitting of hour 13

(n) fitting of hour 14

(o) fitting of hour 15

(p) fitting of hour 16

(q) fitting of hour 17

(r) fitting of hour 18

(s) fitting of hour 19

(t) fitting of hour 20

(u) fitting of hour 21

(v) fitting of hour 22

(w) fitting of hour 23

(x) fitting of hour 24

The following table describes the statistics conducted to select the frequency PSD curve, the variance is calculated two ways once with the variance of the generated frequency signal and another with integrating the PSD curve, the standard deviation of the ROCOF of the generated signal, and the error is also calculated with the help of Eq. 6.1, which could be written as follows:

$$error_{S,i} = \frac{(S_{eq,i} - S_{PSD-integ.,i}) * 100\%}{S_{PSD-integ.,i}} \quad (6.1)$$

Hour	$S_{eq.}$	$S_{PSD-integ.}$	$error_S$	σ_{ROCOF}
1	0.9897	1.0749	-7.9253	0.32998
2	0.98452	1.0731	-8.2562	0.34393
3	0.98111	1.072	-8.4749	0.35345
4	0.98794	1.0743	-8.0374	0.33464
5	0.99358	1.0762	-7.6795	0.31996
6	0.99795	1.0777	-7.4037	0.30904
7	0.98899	1.0746	-7.9707	0.33186
8	0.98579	1.0736	-8.1748	0.34045
9	0.98409	1.073	-8.2832	0.34509
10	0.98619	1.0737	-8.1489	0.33935
11	0.98575	1.0735	-8.1773	0.34056
12	0.98652	1.0738	-8.128	0.33846
13	0.98715	1.074	-8.0878	0.33676
14	0.98406	1.073	-8.2853	0.34518
15	0.98889	1.0746	-7.9771	0.33213
16	0.99516	1.0768	-7.5795	0.31596
17	1.0065	1.0807	-6.8684	0.28884
18	0.9981	1.0778	-7.3947	0.30869
19	0.99919	1.0782	-7.3259	0.30603
20	1.0057	1.0805	-6.9174	0.29064
21	1.003	1.0795	-7.0897	0.29704
22	1.0034	1.0797	-7.0601	0.29593
23	0.99715	1.0775	-7.4541	0.31101
24	0.99472	1.0766	-7.6076	0.31708

Table 6.11: statistics of all fittings